

Electrochemical Behaviour of Mixed Complexes of Indium(III) with 2,2'-Bipyridyl and Thiourea— A Polarographic Study

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Manuscript received 19 October 1984, revised 10 November 1986, accepted 17 February 1986

Polarographic measurements have been used to determine overall formation constants of simple and mixed complexes of In^{III} with 2,2'-bipyridyl and thiourea at $26 \pm 1^\circ$. The reduction of metal and its complexes in 1.0 M KCl and at pH 4.5 on a d.m.e. is reversible and diffusion-controlled. Three mixed ligand species, viz. $[\text{In}(\text{Bip})(\text{Tu})]^{2+}$, $[\text{In}(\text{Bip})(\text{Tu}_2)]^{2+}$ and $[\text{In}(\text{Bip})_2(\text{Tu})]^{2+}$ have been found in the system and their stability constants calculated; the values being $\log \beta_{11} = 4.95$, $\log \beta_{12} = 5.36$ and $\log \beta_{21} = 6.27$, respectively. The tendency of various complexes to add and substitute another ligand is also discussed.

THERE has been an appreciable interest in In^{III} complexes with polyfunctional ligands containing carboxylic group¹⁻³. In the course of our studies on mixed ligand complexes of metal ions with various ligands, we have earlier reported the formation of a series of mixed ligands complexes with bidentate ligands such as amino acids and simple dicarboxylic acids⁴⁻⁶. However, in spite of several studies on mixed complexes, the literature lacks in data on the mixed ligand complexes of In^{III} ion with 2,2'-bipyridyl and thiourea. It therefore seemed desirable to obtain some information about the complexing ability of the 2,2'-bipyridyl and thiourea with In^{III} , particularly from the standpoint of metal—ligand interaction and to describe the preferential formation of mixed complexes.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade and their solutions prepared in double-distilled water. The ionic strength was maintained constant at $\mu = 1.0$ adjusting with KCl solution. A 0.01% gelatin solution was used as maximum suppressor. The concentration of In^{III} was kept at $1 \times 10^{-5} M$. The solution of 2,2'-bipyridyl was prepared in diluted HCl.

Polarograms were obtained on a C.I.C. (Baroda, India) automatic pen recording polarograph. The capillary characteristic were $m = 2.373 \text{ mg s}^{-1}$ at a drop time $= 3.0 \text{ s}^{-1}$ at 40 cm effective height of mercury column in open circuit $m^{3/8} t^{1/8} = 2.136 \text{ mg}^{3/8} \text{ s}^{-1/8}$. A Elico LI-120 digital pH meter

with an assembly of glass and calomel electrode was used to measure the pH of the test solutions. Purified nitrogen gas was used to remove the dissolved oxygen. All measurements were made at $26 \pm 1^\circ$, and at pH 4.5 (adjusted with NaOH—HCl); the pK_a value of 2,2'-bipyridyl under the reported experimental set up.

Results and Discussion

Under the prescribed experimental conditions, In^{III} gave a reversible and diffusion-controlled wave in 1.0 M KCl used as supporting electrolyte. The reduction of In^{III} with bipyridyl and thiourea, separately, was found to be reversible and diffusion-controlled. The same was true in case of mixed systems. The plot of $\log i/(i_a - i)$ vs $E_{a.e.}$ for each polarogram was found to be linear with slope value of 20 mV, indicating the reversibility of the electrode process involving three electrons.

In^{III}—bipyridyl system: In each solution, the concentration of In^{III} was maintained constant at 1 mM while that of bipyridyl varied from 0.01 to 0.1 M. The half-wave potential of In^{III} increased in the presence of bipyridyl to more electronegative value indicating complex formation. The relationship between $-(E_{1/2})_c$ and $\log C_L$, where C_L is the ligand concentration, was not linear but a smooth curve with three segments showing the existence of 1:1, 1:2 and 1:3 complex species. A treatment⁷ of the observed polarographic data revealed the following values for stability constants: $\log \beta_{10} = 3.11$, $\log \beta_{20} = 4.30$ and $\log \beta_{30} = 5.54$.

TABLE 1—POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS AND $F_{1j}[X]$ FUNCTIONS OF In^{III} —2,2'-BIPYRIDYL—THIOUREA MIXED SYSTEM

$\text{In}^{\text{III}}=1 \text{ mM}$, $\mu=1.0 \text{ M KCl}$, Gelatin=0.01%, $\text{pH}=4.50 \pm 0.02$, $\text{Temp.}=26 \pm 1.0^\circ$, Thiourea=0.1 M Fixed

Sl. no.	Concn. of bipyridyl (M)	$-E_{1/2}$ V vs SOE	i_d div	$F_{00}[X] \times 10^{-2}$	$F_{10}[X] \times 10^{-4}$	$F_{20}[X] \times 10^{-5}$	$F_{30}[X] \times 10^{-7}$
1.	0.00	0.59	90	—	—	—	—
2.	0.02	0.64	82	3.82	1.51	2.55	1.17
3.	0.04	0.652	78	16.43	8.90	7.20	1.76
4.	0.06	0.66	74	44.18	7.23	10.88	1.69
5.	0.08	0.665	72	81.55	10.09	11.86	1.39
6.	0.10	0.670	70	150.60	14.98	13.98	1.37

$A=80$, $B=1.0 \times 10^4$, $C=2.1 \times 10^5$, $D=1.4 \times 10^7$.

TABLE 2—POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS AND $F_{1j}[X]$ FUNCTIONS OF In^{III} —2,2'-BIPYRIDYL—THIOUREA MIXED SYSTEM

$\text{In}^{\text{III}}=1 \text{ mM}$, $\mu=1.0 \text{ M KCl}$, Gelatin=0.01%, $\text{pH}=4.50 \pm 0.02$, $\text{Temp.}=26 \pm 1.0^\circ$, Thiourea=0.2 M Fixed

Fl. no.	Concn. of bipyridyl (M)	$-E_{1/2}$ V vs SOE	i_d div	$F_{00}[X] \times 10^{-2}$	$F_{10}[X] \times 10^{-4}$	$F_{20}[X] \times 10^{-5}$	$F_{30}[X] \times 10^{-7}$
1.	0.00	0.59	90	—	—	—	—
2.	0.02	0.652	80	16.02	4.4	1.25	—
3.	0.04	0.660	75	43.55	9.1	1.78	1.96
4.	0.06	0.667	72	103.0	16.0	2.98	2.22
5.	0.08	0.675	70	270.5	32.93	3.86	3.68
6.	0.10	0.680	69	492.9	48.59	4.65	3.65

$A=700$, $B=20 \times 10^4$, $C=1.0 \times 10^6$, $D=2.5 \times 10^7$.

In^{III} —thiourea system: The concentration of thiourea was varied from 0.02 to 0.16 M, other conditions being identical with those maintained in the above system. The shift in $E_{1/2}$ of In^{III} to a more negative value with increasing concentration of thiourea indicated the complex formation. Three complex species were detected with their overall stability constants, $\log \beta_{01}=1.17$, $\log \beta_{02}=3.44$ and $\log \beta_{03}=5.20$.

In^{III} —bipyridyl—thiourea mixed system: Two concentrations of thiourea 0.1 and 0.2 M were chosen for the study of mixed ligand systems. The concentration of 2,2'-bipyridyl was varied from 0.0 to 0.1 M. It was seen that half-wave potential shifted to more negative value as compared to the shift obtained in presence of thiourea only, which revealed the formation of mixed complexes. The method of Schaap and McMasters⁹ was used to determine the composition and values of stability constants of mixed complexes. The polarographic characteristics and $F_{1j}[X]$ functions of mixed complexes of In^{III} with bipyridyl and thiourea (fixed) have been presented in Tables 1 and 2. The functions A , B , C and D were evaluated by Leden's extrapolation method⁹. Three mixed complexes, viz. $[\text{In}(\text{Bip})(\text{Tu})]^{3+}$, $[\text{In}(\text{Bip})_2(\text{Tu})_2]^{3+}$ and $[\text{In}(\text{Bip})_2(\text{Tu})]^{3+}$ with stability constants $\log \beta_{11}=4.95$, $\log \beta_{12}=5.36$ and $\log \beta_{21}=6.27$, respectively, have been observed.

The equilibrium constant K_M for the reaction,

indicated the relative stability of mixed complexes in solution as compared to the parent bis-complexes. The mixing constant (K_M) and stabilisation constant (K_S) have been calculated by the following equation^{10,11},

$$K_M = \beta_{11} / \sqrt{\beta_{22}\beta_{02}} \quad (2)$$

$$\log K_S = \log K_M - \log 2 \quad (3)$$

The calculated values of $\log K_M$ and $\log K_S$ are 1.021 2 and 0.722, respectively. The positive values of mixing constant and stabilisation constants show that the mixed complexes are somewhat more stable than the simple binary complexes. Disproportion constant for the reaction,

was found to be -1.16. The negative value clearly indicates preferential tendency of In^{III} to form mixed complex species $[\text{In}(\text{Bip})(\text{Tu})]^{3+}$ over simple binary complexes. The tendency of ligand to add to a complex and to substitute another ligand is shown in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1. Complex equilibria in ternary system, In^{III}-bipyridyl-thiourea: X=2,2'-bipyridyl and Y=thiourea.

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